
DETERMINANTS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS' UTILIZATION OF DIGITALIZED TEACHING AND LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN OSUN STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study was undertaken to assess the determinants of English Language Teachers' Competency of Digitalized Teaching and Learning Resources in Osun State. Generally, The way of learning and teaching has been improved by the development of digitalized teaching and learning resources. 304 copies of a well structured questionnaire were to elicit information from English language teachers. Data were analysed using correlation and regression techniques. Research results showed that there were seven factors that had an impact in using digitalized teaching and learning resources in teaching English subject, which are: facilitation, motivation, performance, behavioural, social, pedagogical, and effort factors. Also, the study proves that teachers had positive and significant perceptions of digitalized teaching and learning technologies, but still need more supplements and supports.

Keywords: Digitalized teaching and learning technologies, teachers' Utilisation competency, determinants, English Language

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INTRODUCTION

E-learning is the use of media components such as words and pictures to convey content and knowledge. Digitalized teaching and learning technologies have emerged as a necessity to meet the challenges posed by the development of information technology in education (Burnett (2016)). The utilization of multi-media technologies in teaching and learning is necessary and important nowadays due to its capability to deliver input learning easily. Multimedia refers to channels, gadgets, and machines, which transmit information to learners. It includes text, graphics, videos, audios and pictures (Adako, 2016).

Paper-Factors Influencing the Use of Multimedia Technologies in Teaching English Language...that students acquire language better from input enhanced by text and pictures than with text alone. The utilization of information communication technologies in learning improves the learning skills and transforms the way of teaching as well as learning across the board. It develops principles and increases participation between students and their instructors. Moreover, it improves results in students' levels. Recently, applying technology in teaching is essential and becomes an important part of education (Aderonu, 2019).

Alliance for Excellent Education (2020) sees Digitized learning as any instructional practice that effectively uses technology to strengthen students learning experience. Digitization has been acknowledged globally as one of the greatest techniques incorporated into teaching-learning process that brings effective and efficient teaching and learning. For business education students to meet up with the 21st century job skills, digitalized learning and its technological resources has to be implemented fully (Fitzgenrald and Warner (2016)).

Digital learning is a learning facilitated by technology that gives students some element of control over time, place, path and/or space. Time here refers to learning that is no longer restricted to the school day or the school year (Kaku, 2019). The internet access devices have given the students the ability to learn anytime. Digital learning gives access to students to learn in their own style, making learning personal and engaging. Digital learning also makes education more accessible and affordable to students on campus and also worldwide. On 21st century jobs, digital learning enables today's youth to learn technology eagerly and acquire those skills forecasted to remain in the future job spotlight (Ndiku, 2016). Further, digital learning helps students to learn more efficiently, learn more fully and learn with mastery (Sam, 2020).

For digital learning to accomplish its effectiveness, digital learning resources has to be fully implemented into school program. Digitized Learning Resources (DLR) are diverse set of electronic technologies, technological tools and resources utilized to communicate, disseminate, store and manage information in the course of teaching and learning (Nwasuku, 2016). Digitized learning technologies are used to bring about effective and efficient teaching and learning.

Digital learning resources involve the utilization of computer and other electronic devices to pass information to learners. Some of Digital Learning Resources include computer, internet facilities, e-mail services, satellite, telephone, wireless technology, motion picture, overhead projector, interactive board, public address system, printer, scanner, projection screen, television, Local Area Network (LAN), Wide Area Network (WAN), radio, maintenance workshop, spare parts and accessories rooms (Obodo, 2017).

Internet as a digital tool of DLR has strengthen teaching and learning as it provides powerful resources and services for students, thereby enabling them meet their educational needs. It

also allows for networking among students and teachers to facilitate exchange of ideas and improve opportunities for connecting schools to the world as learning is expanding beyond the classroom so real life context can be established (Dotimi & Hamilton-Ekeke, 2021). The internet is the inter connection of system of subsystems of equipment that is used in the automatic acquisition, storage, manipulation, management, movement, control, display, switching, interchange, transmission or reception of data or information. Instructionally, it helps students to learn ahead of content or topic to be covered in the next class. The internet also assists teachers and students to get more meaning about the concept learnt or taught in lesson. The internet also helps the teachers to get more learning resources (teaching resources) beyond the teachers' provision. It also plays a vital role in making research about the topic allocated to students (Otu, 2019). Through the internet, students are taught electronic commerce which involves buying and selling and making of money. Also, the internet exposes the students to electronic learning. The internet has some functions in education which are: (i) Storehouse of information, (ii) Communication without boundaries, (iii) Online interactive learning, (iv) Electronic/Online research, (v) Innovation in the new world, (vi) Improving interest in learning, (vii) Global education and information categories (Park, 2019).

Apart from the internet, in this digital age, the importance of computer cannot be over emphasized for teaching and learning. Computer can be seen as any electronic device that allows students to access the internet to research, create and complete work. This means that a laptop or tablet can be categorized as a classroom computer. Before computers were common in the classroom, teachers would stand in front of class and talk endlessly about a subject. Now computers are used with projectors to show students videos, images and text that are interesting and relevant to what is being taught. Computer helps to replace writing on the chalkboard. Instead of writing on the board, instructor or student takes note on the computer and projects this into the screen so that the whole class can see this. Computer enables the students to read what has been written more easily than instructor's handwriting. With the help of the computer, academic work learnt can then be saved as a record of class then e-mailed to the whole class or posted on the course Web page (Otu, 2019).

Another technological tool that is useful in teaching and learning is the electronic mail (e-mail). With the help of the e-mail, the instructor can provide an updates and reminder to students. Assignments to be carried out by the students can be sent to their e-mails and submitted through the e-mail of the lecturer. Also, vital information and messages can be communicated through the e-mails. New ideas, suggestions and academic progress can be communicated through the e-mails (Okwudishu, 2016).

Apart from the e-mails, interactive whiteboards (smart boards) have exceptionally grown in popularity over the past few years. Schools are discovering that these interactive whiteboards are effective tools for improving learning, communication and collaboration. They offer several advantages over traditional whiteboards which have been used in classrooms for decades to share information and ideas with group members. The interactive whiteboards operate in the connection between a computer, a projector and a touch screen electronic whiteboard. At the heart of the interactive whiteboards, lies a touch screen smart board which students can use the touch screen whiteboard to experiment, solve, write and erase applications such as visual experiments, visuals, animations and graphics. Electronic microscopes, multimedia materials, videos, data tables, CR-ROM or the internet may be used depending on the software programs used by those whiteboards (Miller, Glower & Averis, 2021). Today, Education ministries in many countries are now encouraging the use of interactive whiteboards in classroom.

Wireless technology tool is another DLR which has great impact on teaching and learning. With the introduction of wireless technologies in education system, it has become easier for teachers to impart knowledge and for students to acquire the knowledge. The use of Wireless technology has made the process of teaching and learning enjoyable. Wireless technology also gives access to digital library system which made it easier to store information and it has become a substitute for chalk, board, books and notebooks. Wireless technology has enhanced easy access of information. The internet is a huge information base that can be used as an effective tool for acquiring knowledge through wireless technology (Wellington, 2016).

Despite the fact that digital learning resources has significant roles to play in skills acquisition, there are impediments which may have hindered their use for acquisition of skills by undergraduate business education students in Colleges of Education in Delta State. These includes inadequate digital learning resources, inadequate education curriculum to meet up with the current technological development, poor funding of the institutions by government, inadequate trained personnel, inadequate physical resources and epileptic power supply (Udoh, 2015). These issues as they affect digital learning resources are what this research is set out to investigate.

This research mainly was undertaken to determine the factors that influenced the use of digitalized teaching and learning technologies in teaching English language in Osun State. Specifically, it examined the following: What are the effective factors influencing the use of digitalized technologies in teaching English language in Osun State? Do digitalized teaching and learning technologies increase teachers' motivation? Do digitalized teaching and learning technologies facilitate the teachers' work? Does the social factor affect teachers' behaviour to use digitalized technologies in teaching? Do digitalized teaching and learning technologies increases the teachers' motivation?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research used survey questionnaire method that was distributed to both male and female teachers in the selected public schools in Osun State. The data collected were analysed using correlation and regression techniques.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that most of the English language teachers have excellent use of digitalized teaching and learning resources. The table also shows that awareness of digitized teaching and learning resources is very good. In contrast, demographic variables had no effect on the use of digitalized teaching and learning resources, which gives a sign about equality in effort and efficiency between males and females. In addition, the validity confirms internal consistence. This reflects reasonable results for the study.

Table 1: The distribution of the sample according to the personal variables

Variable	Segment	Count	Percentage
Age Categories	Less than 12 years	34	11.2%
	Between 13-15 years	134	44.1%
	Between 16-18 years	98	32.2%
	19 years or more	38	12.5%
	Total	304	100.0%
Gender	Male	35	11.5%
	Female	269	88.5%
	Total	304	100.0%
Digitalized teaching and learning Technologies' Experience	Fair	4	1.3%
	Good	32	10.5%
	Very Good	133	43.8%
	Excellence	135	44.4%
	Total	304	100.0%

Table 2 shows that the person correlations for the variables are positive and statistically significant. Also

Table 2: Pearson Correlation between each item dimension means

Dimension	Question	Pearson Correlation
Facilitation	1	915**
	2	636**
Social	1	560**
	2	680**
	3	603**
	4	717**
Knowledge	1	546**
	2	788**
	3	744**
Time	1	152**
	2	449**
	2	585**
	3	642**
Performance	1	830**
	2	874**
Motivation	1	900**
	2	437**
	3	866**
Pedagogical	1	842**
	2	839**
Effort	1	774**
	2	809**
Financial	1	478**
	2	702**
	3	226**
	4	567**
Technical	1	708**

	2	744**
	3	428**
Behavioural	1	884**
	2	917**

Table 3: Pearson correlation between behavioural factor and the other factors

Factor	Sample size	Pearson Correlation	P-value
Facilitation	304	** .347	.000
Social	304	** .413	.000
Knowledge	304	.110	.054
Time	304	* -.133	.021
Performance	304	** .526	.000
Motivation	304	** .582	.000
Pedagogical	304	** .513	.000
Effort	304	* -.128	.025
Financial	304	** .151	.008
Technical	304	.002	.973

Table 4: Hypotheses result summary

Hypotheses	Result (supported/Rejected)	Relationship Strength
H₁ : Facilitation factor has an effective impact on digitalised technologies used in teaching English Language.	Supported	Average B=.110
H₂ : Social factor has an effective impact on using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Supported	Average B=.217
H₃ : The Knowledge has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Rejected	No influence
H₄ : Time has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Rejected	No influence
H₅ : Teacher's performance has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Supported	Strong B=.246
H₆ : Motivation has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Supported	Strong B=304
H₇ : The pedagogical factor has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Supported	Strong B=128
H₈ : Effort factor has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Supported	Weak B=-.097
H₉ : The financial factor has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Rejected	No influence

H₁₀ : The technological factor has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Rejected	No influence
H₁₁ : Demographic factor: Age, gender, and experience.	Rejected	No influence
H₁₂ : The behavioural factor has an effective impact in using digitalised technologies in teaching English Language.	Supported	Linear regression

Discussion

This section presents the findings and answers the research questions in the light of conducted data analysis, as follows: What are the effective factors influencing the usage of multimedia technologies in teaching English language in middle public schools in Osun State? Based on the correlation and regression tests that were carried out, there are some factors having relation and others that have no impact. According to ANOVA and Co-efficient Regression tests, there are five factors having no relation in the study, which are; knowledge, financial, technical, time, and demographic factors, which include; age, gender, and experience variables. On the contrary, seven factors had relation in the study. These factors were facilitation, social, motivation, performance, effort, and behavioural factors. All the related factors are positive except effort, which reflects negative weak Paper-Factors Influencing the Use of digitized teaching and learning Technologies in Teaching English Language.

These factors replicate the importance of using digitalized teaching and learning technologies in teaching. These are the factors that are significant to teachers in Osun State if they intent to use digitalized teaching and learning technologies in their classrooms. Therefore, there is strong positive statistically significant correlation between the behavioural factor and the utilization of digitalized teaching and learning technologies with these factors. Regression between the behavioural factor and the other factors is valid, F-test= 26.4 and the P-value =0, P-value < 0.05. The result reflects the positive influence the behavioural factor has in using digitalized teaching and learning technologies in teaching and learning. Does the digitalized teaching and learning technologies increases teachers' motivation? The description of means and statistical analysis for the questionnaire shows agreement in responses, which reflects strong and positive attitude towards using multimedia technologies in increasing teachers' motivation (B = 0.304). On the other hand, the correlation test which should be with P-values <.05, shows strong relation with (.582) value, because teachers find big motivation in using digitalized teaching and learning technologies., Moreover, government departments should pay attention to improve teacher motivation by encouraging teacher to use digitalized teaching and learning technologies by managing workshops and training courses. They also must provide materials and technical support to raise the level of education in our schools. Do the digitalized teaching and learning technologies facilitate teachers' work? It is important to measure the abilities of digitalized teaching and learning technologies in enhancing and simplifying the teachers' work. The statistical analysis for the survey about this question indicates positive effect and strong relation with (B = 0.110). The relation shows positive average regression. There is an average positive relation between behavioural intention and facilitation factor, which reflects the confident power of multimedia technologies in teaching. Also, the correlation results show affirmative relation between behavioural and facilitation factors with P-value = 0.000 < 0.05 value. This reflects strong impact of digitalized teaching and learning on teaching process. The answer of this question confirms the significance of using digitalized teaching and learning technologies in teaching English language. Therefore,

teachers must use digitalized teaching and learning technologies in their work as facilitation aid side by side with their curriculum book and traditional teaching materials. Does the technical issue affect teachers to use digitalized teaching and learning technologies? The means and the statistical analysis of survey confirm nearly neutral responses. The ministry should give schools continuous maintenance and technical support for all technology aids. Also, they must provide all the requirements of modern technology in schools. Teachers must not buy any educational aid from their own money. As the correlation results, there is no relation between the utilization of digitalized teaching and learning technologies and technical factor. The correlation value is (0.002). The p-value is (0.973), which reflects no relation.

Paper-Factors Influencing the Use of Multimedia Technologies in Teaching English Language of technology is very important in the classrooms. Technical problems still needs productive solutions. Also the educational institutions must overcoming the finance and the technical problems in setting up the infrastructure and not allowing the teachers to fear from using it, which leads at the end to lack of motivation.

Does the social factor affect teachers' behavioural intention to use digitalized teaching and learning technologies in teaching? The means and the statistical analysis of survey shown above agreement level, which reflects the positive value of this factor. Also it shows the cooperative society in educational environment. Teachers inside their field of work can learn from each other and exchange information as well as experiences. In addition, the relationship between the social factor and the behavioural to use multimedia technologies is studied by both correlation and regression. The results show supported value with P-value (0.000) and the correlation is (0.413), which reveals the pessimistic outlook the society carries about multimedia technologies. It also shows the lack of awareness of the surrounded society in educational institutions. This is leads to the fact that Osun State still new born in using technology in education. These proofs support the previous studies about technology awareness and usage in education. What is the effect of multimedia technologies in the level of students' understanding? The one of the most important aim of multimedia language in teaching is to encourage students and inspire their motivation to learn. Without multimedia technology, English language learners are often left to their own devices. The answer of this question is positive because the results show strong correlation of performance (0.526) with p-value=0.000<0.05; pedagogy correlation (0.513), p-value=0.000 <0.05; and facilitation factors correlation (0.347) with p-value=0.000<0.05. Therefore, performance of teachers inside the class increases students' understanding. Also, the clarification of curriculum, teaching methods, ways, and styles will be more obvious to students to gain.

Conclusion and recommendation

This study aims to find out the factors influencing use of digitalized teaching and learning technologies through measuring the satisfaction and convenience of the teachers in Osun State. The research used survey questionnaire method that was distributed for both male and female teachers in the selected public schools. The findings show that some factors had influence, which were facilitation, motivation, performance, behavioural, social, and pedagogical and effort factors. However other factors that do not have influence were knowledge, financial, technical, time, and demographic factors. Regarding the improvement of technology, we trust that in future, the use of internet and digitalized teaching and learning technologies in English teaching will be more developed in Osun State. Therefore, the ministry of education must continually and adequately provide digitalized teaching and learning technologies.

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